

Proton-Ligand Stability Constants of Substituted Ortho-Hydroxy Acetophenones and Ortho-Hydroxypropiofenones

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Proton-ligand stability constants of substituted ortho-hydroxyacetophenones and ortho-hydroxypropiofenones were determined at 30° by potentiometric method following Bjerrum Calvin titration technique and using a constant ionic strength, $\mu \sim 0.1M$ NaClO₄. Correlation between the nature and the position of the substituents in benzene nucleus is discussed.

In the investigation of the formation constants of metal complexes it is necessary to determine the proton-ligand stability constants of the reagents. The accurate determination of the proton-ligand stability constants becomes imperative because of the pL values, which are required for the above study, are dependent on these values. The present work on the proton-ligand stability of some substituted ortho-hydroxyacetophenones and ortho-hydroxypropiofenones was undertaken because of our interest in exploring the equilibria which exists when metal ions interact with these reagents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals : (i) Dioxane—A.R. quality of B.D.R. make was purified by the method described by Vogel⁽¹⁾.

(ii) Water—Distilled water was redistilled over alkaline permanganate solution. The resulting distillate was boiled to expel carbon dioxide and cooled in a well stoppered pyrex glass container. The pH of this was 6.8.

(iii) Alkali solution—sodium hydroxide solution free from CO₂ was prepared by the standard method⁽²⁾.

(iv) Chelating agents—(a) 2-hydroxyacetophenone⁽³⁾, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone⁽⁴⁾, 2-hydroxy-4-benzyloxy-acetophenone⁽⁵⁾, 2,6-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone⁽⁶⁾, 2-hydroxypropiofenone⁽⁷⁾, were prepared by known methods. The other reagents, viz., 2-hydroxy 3-methyl-, 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-, and 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy-acetophenones, were obtained from the market, 'FLUKA' A.R. quality. These were further purified by the standard methods and analysed for their purity before use.

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Solutions : Solutions of complexing agents 0.016*M* were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of the compound in dioxane.

Sodium perchlorate solution of 0.8*M* was prepared by adding equivalent amounts of sodium hydroxide in standard perchloric acid.

pH meter and accessories : For the measurements of variations in the *pH* during the course of titration, 'ELICO' *pH* meter, model LI-10 (accuracy ± 0.05 *pH* unit), was used in combination with the glass-saturated calomel electrode assembly. Glass electrode was always kept immersed in 1*M* hydrochloric acid and thoroughly washed with distilled water several times before use. The *pH* meter was calibrated before the beginning of every set of experiment and at the end the calibration was rechecked.

Bubbling of nitrogen : The experiments were carried out in an inert atmosphere of 'oxygen-free' nitrogen, presaturated with the solvent medium, which served to stir the solution as well.

Procedure : The Bjerrum-Calvin *pH*-titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁽⁸⁾ was followed to analyse the equilibria between the ligand, L, shown of all ionizable hydrogen atoms, and protons. Since the reagents were insoluble in water, a 25-75% (v/v) water-dioxane solvent was used. A bulk electrolyte of $\mu \sim 0.1$ *M* sodium perchlorate was adopted to maintain constant ionic strength and reaction solutions were all thermostated at 30° to within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Mixtures consisting of substituted orthohydroxyacetophenone, perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate were titrated with standard alkali. After addition of each portion of alkali, the B value was noted (i.e., *pH* meter reading in mixed solvent) with a glass electrode-saturated calomel electrode combination. Similar titrations were then performed this time without the ligand in the titration mixture.

Calculations : Calculations of \bar{n}_A (the mean number of protons per not-complex bound ligand species) were made by using the expression

$$\bar{n}_A = y - \frac{(V'' - V')}{V^\circ + V'} \cdot \frac{N + E^\circ}{C_A^\circ} \quad \dots (1)$$

where y = the number of dissociable OH present in the ligand molecule,
 V° = Initial volume of the solution,
 E° = Initial concentration of the acid,
 N = Concentration of the alkali used,
 C_A° = Initial total ligand concentration,

V' and V'' = The volume of the alkali needed for reaching the same B values in the two titrations.

In calculating \bar{n}_A values in the present study the quantity 'y' was taken unity since the number of dissociable OH groups present in the reagents is only one as indicated by their

constitutions. The compound 2,6-dihydroxy 4-methyl-acetophenone provided difficulty in the calculation of \bar{n}_A values due to uncertainty in the choice of the values of 'y'. These values, however, have been calculated by choosing $y = 1$, assuming that in this compound only one OH is preferentially dissociable.

Formation curves were obtained from the calculated values on \bar{n}_A and the corresponding 'B' values.

The proton-ligand stability constant was calculated by the following equations :

$$\bar{n}_A + (\bar{n}_A + 1)^P K_1^H \left[\frac{1}{\text{anti log B}} \right] = 0 \quad \dots (2)$$

or

$$\frac{\bar{n}_A}{\bar{n}_A + 1} + {}^P K_1^H \left[\frac{1}{\text{anti log B}} \right] = 0 \quad \dots (3)$$

taking logarithms and rearranging,

$$\log {}^P K_1^H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \quad \dots (4)$$

where, $\log {}^P K_1^H$ represents the first proton-ligand stability constant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The practical values of proton-ligand stability constants were calculated by using the equation (4). The \bar{n}_A , B data observed in the present study are given in Table 1. The average values of the practical constants obtained by using equation (4) are summarised in column 5 of Table 2. According to Bjerrum⁽⁹⁾ the half integral values of the formation curves are equal to $\log {}^P K^H$ values, where ${}^P K^H$ is the formation constant. Such values have also been calculated and are given in column number 4 of table 2. Verification of the results gave the $\log {}^P K_1^H$ values within the limits of ± 0.02 log units.

Discussion on $\log {}^P K^H$ values with smaller differences in a series may hold true within the experimental errors. Such smaller values have been reported by Hastings and Co-workers⁽¹⁰⁾. According to Person⁽¹¹⁾ the standard test on $K < 3$ may be a failure in many cases of the data reported in the literature which does not necessarily mean that the complexes do not really exist or that their equilibrium constants are drastically different from the reported values. Similar is the case in our present investigation where all the general precautions^(9,12,13) in obtaining the most correct values of \bar{n}_A and $\log {}^P K^H$ at each B value have been taken. The comparison of $\log {}^P K^H$ is restricted to structurally similar compounds with similar substitutions in different positions and not of the whole series under investigation.

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TABLE 1
 Data on B and \bar{n}_A for ligands

2-hydroxyacetophenone										
B	10.75	11.00	11.25	11.50	11.75	12.00	12.25	12.50	12.75	
\bar{n}_A	0.902	0.856	0.796	0.641	0.544	0.430	0.312	0.199	0.101	
2-hydroxy-3-methyl-acetophenone										
B	10.20	10.40	10.60	10.80	11.00	11.20	11.40	11.60	11.80	
\bar{n}_A	0.863	0.798	0.716	0.614	0.550	0.387	0.288	0.206	0.138	
2-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone										
B	9.00	0.25	9.50	9.75	10.00	10.25	10.50	10.75	11.00	11.25
\bar{n}_A	0.980	0.960	0.935	0.896	0.809	0.722	0.587	0.453	0.314	0.206
2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone										
B	9.75	10.00	10.25	10.50	10.75	11.00	11.25			
\bar{n}_A	0.850	0.760	0.643	0.503	0.356	0.241	0.149			
2,6-dihydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone										
B	7.50	7.75	8.00	8.25	8.50	8.75	9.00	9.25	9.50	9.75
\bar{n}_A	0.954	0.930	0.880	0.810	0.708	0.565	0.415	0.292	0.131	0.095
2-hydroxy-4-benzyloxy-acetophenone										
B	9.00	9.25	9.50	9.75	10.00	10.25	10.50	10.75	11.00	11.25
\bar{n}_A	0.955	0.919	0.874	0.788	0.685	0.559	0.417	0.230	0.144	0.124
2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy-acetophenone										
B	10.50	10.75	11.00	11.25	11.75					
\bar{n}_A	0.884	0.828	0.700	0.566	0.284					
2-hydroxypropiofenone										
B	9.75	10.00	10.25	10.50	10.75	11.00	11.25	11.50	11.75	12.00
\bar{n}_A	0.975	0.961	0.924	0.835	0.811	0.695	0.509	0.416	0.228	0.112
2-hydroxy-4-methyl-propiofenone										
B	9.50	9.75	10.00	10.25	10.50	10.75	11.00	11.25	11.50	11.75
\bar{n}_A	0.990	0.980	0.951	0.931	0.845	0.787	0.732	0.543	0.358	0.166

 TABLE 2
 Proton-ligand stability constants

No.	Compound	Quantity calculated	Half integral method	Calculated mean	Literature value
(1)	2-hydroxyacetophenone	OH (dissociation)	11.85	—	11.86
(2)	2-hydroxy-3-methyl-acetophenone	OH	11.00	11.00	
(3)	2-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone	OH	10.66	10.66	
(4)	2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone	OH	10.50	10.50	
(5)	2,6-dihydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone	OH	8.88	8.82	
(6)	2-hydroxy-4-benzyloxy-acetophenone	OH	10.33	10.32	
(7)	2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxy-acetophenone	OH	11.35	11.34	
(8)	2-hydroxypropiofenone	OH	11.38	11.37	
(9)	2-hydroxy-4-methyl-propiofenone	OH	11.30	11.32	

The data reported in the above tables are obtained for the first time in 75% dioxane—25% water (v/v) medium, excepting that for ortho-hydroxyacetophenone which has been reported by Venkatachalam⁽¹⁴⁾. His value, viz., 11.86, agrees very well with the one found in this study.

It would be interesting to examine $\log P K^H$ values of the parent compound, i.e., ortho-hydroxyacetophenone with the values reported for the related compounds viz., phenol⁽¹⁵⁾ and salicylaldehyde⁽¹⁶⁾ (Table 3). The acidity of phenol decreases on ortho-substitution in the order of $H > CHO > COCH_3$. In compound (II) and (III) the H atom of OH is involved in the formation of a hydrogen bond with C = O of the side chain⁽¹⁷⁻²⁰⁾, a part of the six membered ring containing two double bonds, as shown below :

This explains the higher values for compounds (II) and (III). The constant for compound (III) higher than that of (II) may be attributed to the presence of electron donating methyl group on the side chain in compound (III). It is probable that the double bond in benzene transmits this effect to the phenolic oxygen, thus preventing it from ionisation.

TABLE 3
Log P K^H values of structurally similar compounds

No.	Compound	$\log P K^H$
I	Phenol	9.98
II	Salicylaldehyde	10.17
III	ortho-hydroxyacetophenone	11.86

$\log P K^H$ values of the methyl substituted ortho-hydroxyacetophenones may be compared with the corresponding methyl-substituted phenols. The values which are also taken from the literature, are surveyed in Table 4. An examination of these values shows that introduction of a methyl group in phenol decreases the acidity of phenol, however, the same substituent in the ortho-hydroxyacetophenone increases the acidity of the parent compound. This suggests that the inductive effect of the methyl group is more prominent in phenols than in ortho-hydroxyacetophenones.

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TABLE 4

Data on compounds having position similarity of the substituents in the nucleus

Compound	log $^P K^H$	Compound	log $^P K^H$
Phenol	9.98	2-hydroxyacetophenone	11.85
Ortho-methyl phenol	10.28	2-hydroxy-3-methyl-acetophenone	11.00
Meta-methyl phenol	10.08	2-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone	10.66
Para-methyl phenol	10.19	2-hydroxy-methyl-acetophenone	10.50

In compound (4), the charge transferred to the oxygen atom from $-\text{COOH}_3$ group appears to be further transmitted to the para position with respect to the $-\text{OH}$ in the benzene nucleus. This stabilizes the phenoxide ion, 5-methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone and thus accounts for the lower values of log $^P K^H$ for this compound. Similarly, the smaller magnitude of log $^P K^H$ for compound (3) indicates that the inductive effect of the methyl group in position para with respect to the $-\text{COCH}_3$ prevents the charge transfer from $-\text{COCH}_3$ to phenolic oxygen, which helps in the ionization of this molecule, due to the formation of a strong hydrogen bond between ketonic oxygen and phenolic $-\text{H}$. The same reasoning accounts for lower magnitude of the log $^P K^H$ of compound (5).

In compound (7), the two methoxy groups in positions ortho and para with respect to $-\text{COCH}_3$ and having small electron donating mesomeric effect result in smaller differences in log $^P K^H$ values of the parent compound (1) and compound (7).

Of the three methyl-substituted ortho-hydroxyacetophenones, the compound (2) has the highest value of log $^P K^H$ but it is lower than that of the parent compound. In this case the authors feel that the mesomeric effect of the OH group is only slightly greater than the inductive effect of the methyl group. This permits the ionization of compound (2) to some extent thus giving a relatively lower value of $^P K^H$ for this compound. This reasoning appears to be supported by the observed values of log $^P K^H$ for compound (4) in which the methyl group is at a further distance from the $-\text{OH}$ group. In this case the mesomeric electron donating action of OH group as against the inductive effect of the methyl group is much greater than that in compound (2) which thus accounts for the lowest proton-ligand stability constant for compound (4) amongst all the methyl substituted derivatives.

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Received June 7, 1968,
Revised MSS received October 6, 1969.